

HISTORY APPROACH MODEL OF INDONESIAN DEFENSE DIPLOMACY TO INCREASE INDONESIAN CREDIBILITY IN THE SOUTH PACIFIC (HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE OF THE RUSSIA-JAPAN WAR, 1904-1905)

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Abstract

This research aimed to examine academic and historical perspectives of the Russo-Japanese War in 1904-1905 to obtain various models of approaches to Indonesia's defense diplomacy in the South Pacific region. The theory of representation, the theory of regionalism, and the theory of diplomacy itself and supported by the perspective of historical values of the Russo-Japanese war in Tsushima, teach several models of defense diplomacy approaches that are very relevant to be implemented in the South Pacific. This research used a qualitative analytical method by collecting data through a literature review from various sources, such as books, journals, and others, related to diplomacy and the history of the Tsushima War, both from a Russian perspective and a Japanese perspective which is analyzed and discussed to find an Indonesian defense diplomatic approach model. The results show that the analysis of the theories and values of Russian and Japanese diplomacy can be used as a reference to become a model for Indonesian defense diplomacy in the South Pacific region to increase Indonesia's credibility.

Keywords: defense diplomacy, South Pacific, war history.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Indonesia's diplomacy is projected to be very busy in the era of President Joko Widodo's leadership until 2024. Indonesia will occupy key positions in several regional and global organizations, namely as Chair of ASEAN and Chair of the G-20. Indonesia is also committed to further promoting its role and contribution as a member of the UN Security Council and Human Rights Council, as well as the International Maritime Organization. Participation in the global political arena is the implementation of national goals to participate in maintaining world peace, based on the principles of independence, eternal peace, and social justice (Fawaid, 2020).

Indonesia's diplomacy since President Soekarno (1945-1967) to President Joko Widodo era (2014-2024) showed an increasing and expanding graph that is implemented in various bilateral and multilateral cooperation, such as the Non-Aligned Movement, the Asian-African Conference (Strydom, 2007), NEFO (Nugroho, 2016), ASEAN, APEC (APEC, 2019), ARF, ASEM, EAS, IORA (Rosyidin, 2019), and others. Then, Joko Widodo's government era began

with great momentum through the declaration of the Global Maritime Fulcrum at the East Asia Summit in Myanmar in 2014 (Yanyan Mochamad Yani, 2015).

The Global Maritime Fulcrum policy is in line with an inward-looking foreign policy to realize a sovereign, independent, and personal Indonesia based on cooperation. Indonesia has proven leadership as Chair of the IORA for the period 2015-2017, and a Non-Permanent Member of the UN Security Council for the period 2019-2020 (Indonesia Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2019).

1.2 Problems

Indonesia's membership in various international organizations and fora is a manifestation of free and active foreign policy diplomacy as formulated by the founding fathers to increase Indonesia's credibility as a sovereign state and freedom to determine its destiny. However, these diplomatic activities are still dominated by the Asian and Indian Ocean regions, not yet optimized to reinforce Indonesia's diplomacy, especially in the South Pacific region where this credibility has been undermined by the antipathy attitude of South Pacific countries in the last six years.

Since 2016, Vanuatu together with the Solomon Islands, Tonga, Nauru, Marshall Islands, and Tuvalu (Tuwo, 2016) have criticized Indonesia's human rights record in Papua at the UN General Assembly which urged Indonesia to give the right to determine the fate for Papua. In 2017, Vanuatu brought up the same issue at the 72nd UN General Assembly. In 2019, the Prime Minister of Vanuatu, Charlot Salwai Tabimasmass, said there were allegations of human rights violations in Papua at the 74th UN General Assembly. Tabimasmass hoped that the UN can find a solution to solve the problem and come to Papua to investigate the current conditions. Vanuatu even deliberately helped bring Benny Wenda into the UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (UN OHCHR) in Geneva. Benny is the leader of the United Liberation Movement for West Papua (ULMWP). In 2020, Vanuatu brought up the same issue again through a speech by the Prime Minister of Vanuatu, Bob Loughman (Arbar, 2020).

The chairman of the Pacific Islands Forum (PIF), Tuvaluan Prime Minister Kausea Natano, has written to the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights Michelle Bachelet, requesting support for the PIF request to send a mission to assess the human rights situation in Papua. The forum chair reiterated the PIF leaders' call to all parties to protect and uphold the human rights of all citizens and work to address the root causes of the conflict by peaceful means (Mcdonald, 2020).

Indonesia's diplomacy with Melanesian countries that are members of the Melanesian Spearhead Group (MSG) which consists of four sovereign countries, namely Fiji, Papua New Guinea, Solomon Islands, and Vanuatu, has increased Indonesia's status from observer to associate member. The MSG, founded in 1988 as a forum for cooperation on important regional Melanesian issues, also includes the Front de Libération Nationale Kanak et Socialiste (FLNKS), a political party in New Caledonia seeking independence from France, as well as the ULMWP as the observer (Wyeth, 2017).

Based on the description, this paper intends to explain the Indonesian defense diplomacy approach model in the South Pacific Region which was adopted from the defense diplomacy approach models obtained from an academic perspective and historical values of the Russo-Japanese war in 1904-1905. The method used to examine the problem is literature research by studying various books, journals, or other sources related to the History of the Russo-Japanese War (1904-1905). The author examines and analyzes using qualitative analysis using the content analysis method, namely reading, reviewing the content, interpreting, and trying to reveal the meaning contained, then discussing the relevant diplomacy values developed into a model of Indonesia's defense diplomacy approach.

2. THEORY BASIS

2.1 Regional Theory

The involvement of the Military 'Pacific' Command is actually in line with the theory of regionalism and representation theory because it is an area that historically has many physical similarities, making it easier to unite to continue to exist and the possibility of efforts to perpetuate the Region. A region is defined as a group of geographically close countries because they are in a certain area (Snyder, 2008). Bjorn Hettne and Fredrik Soderbaun suggest that geographical proximity is strongly supported by cultural similarities, social ties, and the same history (Bjorn Hettne, 2002).

The provinces of East Nusa Tenggara, Maluku, North Maluku, Papua, and West Papua fully meet these three requirements and serve as examples to pioneer again so that the South Pacific region, especially Melanesia, becomes a group of countries that strengthen themselves as the same region, namely the South Pacific region which have the same intensity of interaction and progress between one region and another. Indonesia's defense diplomacy in the South Pacific must implement the New Regional Theory (Hettne, 2000), namely the development of regionalism depends on three points. They support Indonesia as a great power in the region, increasing the intensity of interaction between countries in the region, and building cooperation, and international trust in the region. The support of Indonesia's presence is expected to be able to make the South Pacific region more peaceful and have a good and strong interaction relationship.

Indonesia's geographical dimension is a vital character for Indonesia's security and prosperity in the 21st century which needs to be supported by a model of defense diplomacy that is expected to be able to influence Indonesia's interests in the South Pacific region which has the same regional character as an island nation, ethnicity, and climate.

Sir Ernest Satow (1922) defined diplomacy as the application of intelligence and tactics to carry out official relations between sovereign governments, while Barston defines diplomacy as the management of relations between states and other international relations actors. The defense diplomacy model is formulated in a cultural approach to reach an agreement, compromise, and resolve problems in the respective national interests (Djelantik, 2008).

The defense diplomacy model with a cultural approach includes the exchange of ideas, information, arts, and other cultural aspects to foster mutual understanding as an important component of broader diplomacy. The cultural approach in the form of fun creative expressions is the implementation of 'soft power diplomacy' with contemporary (millennial) cultural characteristics, in making technology a lifestyle, multitalented, multilingual, expressive and explorative, optimistic, self-confident, simple, interactive, and collaborative (Wahana, 2015). It is not difficult to understand the potential of a cultural approach as Indonesia and the South Pacific Region have similarities in Eastern ethnicities compared to Australia and New Zealand as Western ethnicities.

A cultural approach rooted in ideals and values, covering three modalities. There is a soft power through education and training in defense and security forces by increasing the number of overseas students supported by easier visa and student policies; the cultural approach is a new paradigm of international politics as a form of expression of soft power that projects the Ministry of Defense to be an actor and center of identity; and a model of intergovernmental relations, in this case, the Ministry of Defence, to interact domestically and internationally that is easy to adapt to the external environment quickly with an emphasis on political communication theory using Education and Training media as well as on foreign systems, cooperation with relevant ministries to respond to situations flexibly and quickly. The soft power model with the power of quick reaction will be a positive value in the strategic culture approach as the rationale for the soft power defense diplomacy paradigm. (Melissen, 2005).

3. DISCUSSION

3.1 Indonesia's Credibility in the South Pacific Region

Indonesia's credibility disturbed in the South Pacific region requires defense diplomacy as an inseparable part of state diplomacy in regulating relations between countries to achieve national interests to maintain state sovereignty, territorial integrity of the country, and the safety of all nations. Defense diplomacy is the implementation of the readiness of the state's defense posture based on the integration of strength, capability, and deployment of national resources (Faris Al-Fadhat, 2019). Defense diplomacy in the South Pacific region goes beyond what is stated in the 2015 Defense White Paper which emphasizes international cooperation with Asian, European, and African countries as well as the United States, Australia, and Papua New Guinea (Indonesia Defense Ministry, 2015).

The phenomenon shows that several defense diplomacy activities that Indonesia participated in the Pacific region were the Rimpac Exercise in Hawaii, the Western Pacific Naval Symposium (WPNS), and the Kakadu Exercise in Darwin. These defense diplomacy activities have not shown the dominant role of the Indonesian government. The only defense diplomacy that has ever been carried out in the South Pacific region was the dispatch of the Indonesian Armed Force in Humanitarian Assistance Operation to rehabilitate and reconstruct the Queen Victoria School (QVS) building in Matavatuou, Fiji, in 2016 (Maritimeneews, 2016).

Morgenthau (1967), for example, said that good diplomacy is the most realistic way for the national interest because it is related to the peaceful achievement of foreign policy goals and takes a broader picture of what needs to be done. Diplomacy makes a foreign policy more efficient, functions as a force multiplier, or is a morally better way of conducting international relations, it can also be implemented through the development of a defense diplomacy model based on representation theory. Representation of defense diplomacy is an anthropological and sociological approach that brings diplomacy at high political levels closer to the practice of everyday life. One of Ragnar Numelin's major early works, *The Beginnings of Diplomacy* (1950), has provided many illustrations of non-state diplomatic activity between ethnic groups and peoples as an overt or subtle way of extending kinship and commonalities, and mediating differences. Interesting contributions from a geographical perspective are used to approach defense diplomacy to increase diplomatic sensitivity (Costas M. Constantinou, 2017).

Geographical and cultural approaches in defense diplomacy need to be optimized by the Indonesia Ministry of Defense and Armed Forces Headquarters. The existence of 'Pacific' Military Commands such as 3rd Defense Territorial Joint Command, 3rd Fleet Command, and 3rd National Air Operations Command and their staff have not automatically become delegates or task forces that represent themselves as Military 'Pacific' Command in activities in the South Pacific Region.

Such representation defense diplomacy needs to be carried out in various forms of international cooperation through new ways by increasing the presence and active role of capacity building measures, capacity building, and strategic partnerships to prevent or reduce the risk of conflict that cause by mistrust, misunderstanding, and miscalculation among South Pacific countries (Hidayat Chusnul Chotimah, 2019), while still prioritizing national interests based on academic perspectives (theories) and analysis of the implementation of Russia and Japan defense diplomacies during the Tsushima War of 1904-1905.

3.2 Adaptation to Sovereignty and Independence in the Contemporary Pacific

Defense diplomacy must also pay attention to the diversity of the constitutional political status of countries in the contemporary Pacific Islands, namely independent countries, commonwealth, and trust territories. Independent countries are Papua New Guinea, Solomon Islands, Vanuatu, Fiji, Western Samoa, Tonga, Kiribati, Tuvalu, and Nauru. Countries that are part of the commonwealth are the Cook Islands and Niue for New Zealand. Trust territories are Guam, Northern Mariana Islands, and Samoa as commonwealth as well as Midway, Wake, Johnston Atoll, Howland Island, and Baker Island, along with the American Line Islands-Kingman Reef, Palmyra Atoll, Easter Island, and Jarvis Island, all administered by the United States; Tokelau is a territory of New Zealand; New Caledonia, French Polynesia, Wallis and Futuna are French overseas territories, and the Provinces of Valparaiso (Chile), Pitcairn Islands (UK) and Norfolk Island (Australia).

Apart from constitutional factors, the great powers (France, the United States of America, the United Kingdom, Australia, and New Zealand) have many interests in the South Pacific Region. France has a very strategic interest in nuclear modernization in French Polynesia and

New Caledonia. The nuclear test centers on the atolls of Moruroa, Fangataufa, and Hao are under the protection of the commander of the French Pacific forces based in Papeete. There are six French nuclear-powered ballistic missile submarines carrying a total of 496 nuclear warheads as well as a nuclear-powered Charles-de-Gaulle-class aircraft carrier. Likewise, the United States and Britain defended the territory across the island for defense purposes. Australia and New Zealand play an important role in security, politics, and economics in the South Pacific. Australia is the largest donor.

Based on the analysis above, Indonesia's defense diplomacy can be focused on sovereign countries, especially Papua New Guinea, Solomon Islands, Vanuatu, Fiji, West Samoa, Tonga, Kiribati, Tuvalu, and Nauru. Meanwhile, with the countries holding the commonwealth and trustees in the South Pacific. They are New Zealand, the United States, France, Chile, the UK, and Australia, which already have a good relationship with Indonesia. (Firth, 1989).

3.3 The failure of Russian diplomacy in Far East Asia sparked the Tsushima War

Before its expansion into Manchuria, Russia needed a warm water port. Russia attempted to take control of Manchuria (a Chinese territory) after failing in Europe and the Middle East. Russia does not want to get a failure like when was not able to dominate the Kurds and Turkey in the Mediterranean. However, Russian diplomacy failed again because Russia ignored South Korea as an unimportant territory.

Russian diplomacy in the Far East region has been done only to satisfy the narcissistic impulses of the personality and needs of the Russian leader, Czar Nicholas II. Czar Nicholas II was so carried away by his first success in controlling Port Arthur on the Manchuria peninsula that he considered the Far East countries, Japan, China, and Korea, as easily conquered countries and only a diversion from the current domestic difficulties experienced by Russia. Expansion to Korea is considered to have high-cost potential and low-benefit economics. Russia abandoned its treaty with Japan over Korean sovereignty after its success in Manchuria. Sergei Witte, Russia's Finance Minister, did not agree with Russia's involvement in South Korea. After the war, Witte stated that if Russia stayed true to the spirit of this treaty, there would be permanent peaceful relations with Japan. Witte wanted to avoid war with Japan, but Nicholas wanted it anyway (B.V. Anan'ich, 2005).

It should be noted that the Russian expansion into the Far East began in the 16th century under Ivan IV, but was not focused. Nicholas had a greater focus on Far East diplomacy to distract from Russia's domestic predicament, but it was too late.

The failure of Russian diplomacy towards Far East Asian countries is due to neglect, lack of focus, and concern over potentially high costs. These values will become lessons learned for implementing Indonesia's diplomacy in the South Pacific.

The Indonesian government must not ignore every issue that disturbs Indonesia's credibility. Indonesian diplomacy must be present in the South Pacific Region, especially geographically, Indonesia is also in this region. Five provinces, East Nusa Tenggara, Maluku, North Maluku, Papua, and West Papua, are Melanesian ethnic and racial communities characterized by dark

skin, curly textured hair, large and sturdy bone structure, and an athletic-looking. According to the Ministry of Education and Culture, the population of the Melanesian race in Indonesia reaches 13 million people, even greater when compared to the Melanesian race in the South Pacific, which is 'only' 9 million people (Seftian, 2020).

Indonesia's defense diplomacy must also focus on the South Pacific Region. The priority of defense diplomacy is to provide education and training in the military field (military operations on war/MOW) and in the fields of search and rescue (SAR), human assistance, and disaster relief (Military Operations Other Than War/MOOTW). The data shows the number of foreign student officers from the South Pacific countries who have attended a high level of military education. In Armed Forces Staff and Command College, there were only 2 officers from Papua New Guinea and New Zealand that equal to 1.77% of the total 113 students; Naval Staff and Command College have 7 students from Papua New Guinea and Fiji, or 2.59% of 270 students, and Air Force Staff and Command College only have 1 student from Papua New Guinea or 0.03% of 325 students. Foreign students can be increased by the approach of providing scholarships or opening English-based international classes at the Armed Forces Staff and Command College or preparing interpreters.

The development of port visit defense diplomacy is carried out by utilizing the Navy warships, especially the training sailing ships KRI Bima Suci and KRI Dewaruci. KRI Bima Suci has a capacity of 200 people, which involves a combined military and non-military cultural team.

3.4 Japan's victory over Russia in the Battle of Tsushima (1904-1905)

Japan began its diplomatic negotiations with Russia on July 28, 1903, regarding Manchuria or Korea. Japan was treated with contempt and arbitrariness by Russia.

Japan-Russia diplomacy failed, and Japan decided to withdraw its Ambassador from St. Petersburg on February 6, 1904 (Berry, 2008). Japan then prepared military intelligence and adequate preparation. Japan-Russia Diplomacy negotiations failed, and Japan decided to withdraw its Ambassador from St. Petersburg on February 6, 1904 (Berry, 2008). Then, Japan prepared its military intelligence.

Carl von Clausewitz (1780-1831) had two views on the military intelligence values that are important for (1) determining the outcome of a conflict; and (2) gathering information to prepare for war (Clausewitz, 1984). Intelligence supported the Japanese military since the end of the Meiji period (1868-1912). Intelligence strongly supports the Japanese Empire in preparing for the war against Russia by forming the Amur Society (Kokuryūkai), a Japanese secret society founded in 1901 led by Uchida Ryōhei.

The Amur Society had two priorities. The first was to prepare for war, and the second softened Japanese public opinion. Uchida also understood the importance of language. Almost no one in Japan could speak Russian. To understand the enemy's plans, one had to be able to translate their language. The Amur Society founded schools for Russian and Chinese. Although the educational value was considered small, eventually some Japanese officers understood Russian and became Japanese military scouts in Manchuria.

More important, the Amur Society created anti-Russian feelings and stimulated pro-war attitudes throughout Japan by publishing the journal 'Kokuryū'. The journal contains anti-Russian aggressiveness. The reality, Japan considered Russia as an enemy and the battle against Russia is supported by the Japanese citizens. Every victory of the Japanese was celebrated. The war is finally won (Jacob, 2016).

Referring to the description above, Indonesia's defense diplomacy can adopt approaches that make Japan win over Russia. The approach includes the preparation of military intelligence personnel, language acquisition, and publications.

The intelligence approach has an important role to increase the superiority of a country's grades. Intelligence combines expertise in secret information with specialized methods of diplomacy. Foreign intelligence intermediary personnel interact with diplomacy and national policy. Defense attaches stationed in appointed countries are assigned to obtain military information to be reported to military intelligence (Chairil, 2015). Indonesia's Defense attaches in the South Pacific are posted in Australia, New Zealand, Papua New Guinea, Fiji, and the Philippines. For countries, such as the Solomon Islands, Vanuatu, Western Samoa, Tonga, Kiribati, Tuvalu, and Nauru, the Indonesian government may consider preparing a defense attache or military attache with the rank of Lieutenant Colonel or Major (Ariesta, 2017).

The ability to speak in Mandarin and Russian language for Japanese intelligence can be analogized to a form of cultural approach in contemporary defense diplomacy. The language ability is very strategic and demands the ability to communicate properly and correctly, especially in English. Defense attaches need high competence in English, other international languages, and/or the language of the local country as the language of instruction and communication. The ability to communicate will make it easier to understand and process actual information from various sources, as well as understand the culture and customs of the South Pacific countries.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

4.1 Conclusions

Based on the analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn.

Indonesia's credibility in the South Pacific requires defense diplomacy as a representation of Indonesia through an anthropological and sociological approach that brings diplomacy at a high political level to the practice of daily life, and a geographical and cultural approach by optimizing the presence of the Military 'Pacific' Command as a delegation that represents itself on defense activities in the region.

Indonesia's defense diplomacy in the South Pacific implements the New Regional Theory, which is the development of regionalism in the form of Indonesia's support as a regional great power, increasing the intensity of interaction, and building mutual trust among countries in the region that has the same character as an island nation, ethnicity, and climate.

The defense diplomacy model with a cultural approach includes the exchange of ideas, information, art, and other cultural aspects to foster mutual understanding as an important component of broader diplomacy. The cultural approach to creative expression is fun and it has a character that makes technology a lifestyle, multitalented, multilanguage, expressive and exploratory, optimistic, self-confident, simple, interactive, and collaborative.

Indonesia's defense diplomacy model must not be ignored, more focus, and prepare the budget for its implementation. As the owner of the largest Melanesian race, Indonesia's diplomacy should not be neglected in the South Pacific, which is focused on education and training in the military (MOW) and in the fields of search and rescue (SAR), humanitarian assistance and disaster relief (HADR), as well as port visit programs.

4.2 Recommendation

Indonesia's defense diplomacy must pay attention to the diversity of the constitutional and political status of the countries in the Pacific contemporary. The independent countries, commonwealth, and trust territory. The priorities are Papua New Guinea, Solomon Islands, Vanuatu, Fiji, Western Samoa, Tonga, Kiribati, Tuvalu, and Nauru, and to great power countries New Zealand, United States, France, Chile, the United Kingdom, and Australia.

The defense diplomacy approach includes the preparation of military intelligence personnel, language acquisition, and publications. The intelligence approach has an important role to increase credibility among countries, and the capability of international languages for intelligence is very strategic and requires the ability to communicate properly and correctly.

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